

DIFFERENTIATION ACTIVITIES FOR MULTI-LEVEL CLASSES

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This article describes how to implement useful classroom activities in teaching foreign languages. Here is given types of activities and how to use them in teaching young learners. So, our research will focus on these areas with the purpose of finding out the way optimizing the teaching effectiveness of Classroom Activities.

Key words: Classroom Activities, interaction Activities, pair working, teaching strategies, evaluation, dialoguing in achievement.

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Introduction

All learners need to be given access to the same core content and taught the same big idea and concept. Differentiating access to content involves adjusting the grade of complexity. For example, if the learning goal/ intention is for all students to write persuasive paragraphs, some of the students might be learning to use a topic sentence and supporting details, while others may be learning to use outside sources to justify their opinion. Differentiating for students' interests involves: illustrate students how the subjects taught deal with their particular interests; helping students discover new interests by providing an encouraging curriculum; aligning key skills and material for understanding with themes or pursuits that interest students, for example, a student can learn much about a local people or time period by carefully analysing its music.

Differentiating process

Process can be thought of as the learning experiences that are designed to give help students make sense of, understand as well as use the content. An effective learning experience involves students in using essential skills to come to an understanding about a critical idea and is clearly focused on a learning intention. For example, one student may independently explore a topic while another may collaboratively work on a task with others.

Differentiating product

Product refers to things a student can use to demonstrate their knowledge understanding and skills. A good product allow student to: apply what they can do; extending their understanding and skill; become involved in critical and creative thinking; reflect on what they have acquired. For example, to built understanding of the plot of a story one student may create a skit while another student writes a book report at the same time.

Purpose and mission

Learning environment refers to the way the classroom works and feels. When differentiating the learning environment the teacher considers the students' 'environmental' preferences. For example, some students need lots of work space, some need a quiet area, some like to engage in discussions, some like to work alone. Interest refers to topics that students may want to explore or topics that will motivate them.

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Interests and motivations are closely linked, and when motivation to learn increases, student outcomes are likely to be more favourable than others who have not got any motivation. To assume there is not time to address student interests is to assume there is no time to motivate students to learn.

To differentiate for student interests: use adults or peers with prior knowledge to serve as mentors in an area of shared interest; provide a variety of avenues for student exploration of a topic or expression of learning; provide broad access to a wide range of materials and technologies; offer a choice of tasks and products, including student-designed options; encourage investigation or application of key concepts and principles in student interest areas; connect content with students' cultures, experiences, and talents; use interest centres, interest groups, specialty groups or expert groups; use jigsaw groups; offer choice in topics for reading materials; offer sub-topic choices within an area of study/ topic.

Learning profiles

Learning profile is shaped by at least 3 overlapping factors: learning style, group and environmental preferences.

Differentiating for learning profiles involves: uncovering student learning profiles; balancing presentations and learning experiences according to learning profiles; offering choice in learning experiences and ways to demonstrate learning.

To differentiate for learning profiles: create a learning environment with flexible spaces and learning options: present information through auditory, visual and kinaesthetic modes; encourage students to explore information and ideas through auditory, visual and kinaesthetic modes; allow students to work alone or with peers; ensure a choice of competitive, cooperative and independent learning experiences; balance varied perspectives on an issue or topic; provide authentic learning opportunities in various intelligence or talent areas; show part-to-whole and whole-to-part relation.

Balance teamwork and individual work in foreign language learning classes teamwork and collaboration occur regularly in a pbl project. We want to leverage collaboration as much as content. However, there are many times when individual instruction and practice may be needed. You need to differentiate the learning environment because some students learn better on their own, and others learn better in a team rather than being alone. In fact, every student all need time to process and think alone just as much as we need time to learn from our peers. Make sure to balance both so that you are supporting a collaborative environment while allowing time to meet students on an individual basis.

As you master the pbl process in your classroom, you will intuitively find opportunity to differentiate instruction for your students. Teacher will design the project to scaffold content and skills in a variety of ways, will create formative and summative assessments to allow for student passions and goals, and will manage the process so that it allows teacher to meet students where they are and move them forward.

Differentiate through formative assessments formative assessments can look the same for all learners. They can also look different than others. We know that students can show what they've learned in different ways, as mentioned above in terms of products produced as summative assessment. In addition, as you check for understanding along the way, you can formatively assess in different ways when appropriate.

Perhaps you are targeting collaboration in the lesson. You can differentiate a formative assessment of this in a variety of ways. Perhaps it's an oral conference or it's a series of written responses. Perhaps it's a graphic collage or organizer. Moreover, these formative assessments allow you to differentiate the type of instruction needed as you feed forward in the project.

Extension Activities are a great strategy for students who had already formed a huge schema for the concepts. Always have an extension activity planned for learners who quickly grasp the concept. By having an extensioning plan, you have the opportunity to provide enrichment to the students who are already grasping the material. Another idea is to incorporate student-learning roles in which students who are quickly grasping the concepts can be the small group helper to those students who want to have additional assistance.

Most of what teachers do in their classrooms is guided by their own philosophy of teaching and teaching methods. Differentiation works best in classrooms where certain beliefs motivate why, what, and how teachers' approach planning for and responding to student differences (Tomlinson, 2014). Four tenets about the capabilities and potentials of all students, and about the role and responsibility of all teachers, represent assumptions of the teachers of a differentiated classroom.

1. Diversity is normal and valuable.

The differentiated classroom teacher understands and accepts that students represent a rich spectrum of diverse experiences and characteristics. Differences should be noticed, not ignored or corrected; they are an asset, not a liability, to the school community. The teacher values students as individuals and as a group based on shared and unique traits.2. Every child has hidden and extensive capacity to learn.

2. The differentiated classroom teacher knows that traditional measures of ability, such as standardized test scores and grades; don't tell the whole story about which a student is or what they can do. The teacher assumes that every student can learn and that a student's greatest strengths may be hidden under the surface and requires the teacher to dig deeper to uncover what will help these students learn and grow.3. It is the teacher's responsibility to be the engineer of student success.

3. The teacher of a differentiated classroom defines student success as growth toward and beyond goals, growth relative to oneself (e.g., where you started compared to where you ended up) as well. This growth does not happen by accident; it is the result of the teacher taking ownership of and intentionally planning for all students' acquiring. Such teacher does not dismiss or minimize a student's chances for success based on (for example) student's English language skills, IEP, or home life. They commit to doing what they can with the time they have to make sure every child grows.

4. Educators should be the champions of each student who enters the schoolhouse doors.

The teacher of a differentiated classroom believes that educators become champions for all students and is an advocate of every child in his/her charge. This includes children who are very easy to miss and those who are very hard to ignore; children who are academically far behind and those far ahead; and children who have many advantages and those who have very little advantage.

These four beliefs lay a philosophical groundwork for differentiation to take roots. It is easy to picture differentiation being implemented in the classroom of teachers who hold these convictions. It is hard, by contrast, to picture differentiation being implemented in the classroom of a teacher who believes that diversities are undesirable or a nuisance; that some children can learn but others cannot; that student success is determined by factors beyond the teacher's controls; or that some children are not reachable or teachable.

Teachers of differentiated classrooms understand that their role has limited, but they are convinced that they have the power and responsibility to effect growth in all children in diverse classrooms.

Homogeneous Grouping does not have these benefits. Students are not strengthening their social skills to work with a variety of learners. Students will be bored working with the

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same students. Some groups and classes are provided inequitable resources or rote, memorization activities. More labeling occurs and even stereotypes result from ability groupings.

Vary activities/ learning experiences

Readiness: A differentiated classroom does not mean teaching students one by one. In a differentiated classroom the teacher attempts to provide enough variety so that learning is a better fit for more students. That is, on one day a teacher may assign one task to students who seem to be having difficulty with a particular idea or skill and another to students who don't seem to be having difficulty

Interests: Think in terms of manageable ranges of options. A range of four interest-based options for students may not be a perfect match for everyone's interests, but having four options is likely to engage more students than if there were no options at all.

Learning profiles: Students may prefer to work alone or with a partner; work in a quiet area for example. Give students a range of manageable options to complete work. Differentiating learning can be enabled by differentiating the teaching approach to content, process, product and the learning environment.

Conclusion:

Flexible grouping is highly encouraged, because students have a chance to flow in and out of groups as they need to throughout the year. Flexible grouping diminishes the stigma of a low group or high level classes. All students are intelligent in different ways and about different subjects and flexible grouping allows students to share their strengths and exchange their experience even.

The easiest and most beneficial way to differentiate your classroom is heterogeneous grouping in learning foreign languages. Cooperative learning groups develop students' skills in critical thinking, positive social interactions, and understanding multiple perspectives. Students will take more motivation when working with students of different learning styles; more opportunities for peer education, which fosters more democratic classroom; same amount of time and resources will be given every group by the teacher because the activities vary in skill and interest. It is important to incorporate flexible mixed ability groupings.

References:

- [1]. Heacox D. (2002) *Differentiation Instruction in the Regular Classroom: How to Reach and Teach All Learners*, Minneapolis, MN: Free Spirit.
- [2]. Heacox, D. (2005). *Promoting Student Independence and Responsibility in Academically Diverse Classrooms*. 2005 ASCD Annual Conference. Orlando, FL.
- [3]. Nunley, K. E. (2006). *Differentiating the High School Classroom: Solution Strategies for 18 Common Obstacles*. Thousand Oaks: CA: Corwin.
- [4]. Tomlinson, C. A., & Allan, S. D. (2000). *Leadership for Differentiating Schools and Classrooms*.
- [5]. Wormeli, R. (2006). *Fair Isn't Always Equal: Assessing & Grading in the Differentiated Classroom*. Portland, ME: Stenhouse.
- [6]. Jensen, E. (1998). *Teaching with the Brain in Mind*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- [7]. Tomlinson, C. 2006. *An Educator's Guide to Differentiating instruction*. Cengage Learning. USA.
- [8]. Tomlinson, C. A. & Allan, S. D. 2000 *Leadership for Differentiating Schools and Classrooms*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD.